

Creating a data management plan
using the SaxFDM Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO)

CLICK-BY-CLICK GUIDE

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1 GENERAL

1.1 What are Data Management Plans (DMPs)?¹

A DMP is a document that provides a structured description of how research data—whether generated or reused—will be managed throughout the course of a project and beyond. A DMP helps to consider and keep track of all aspects of research data management, to estimate the effort involved and to calculate the costs incurred. As a document accompanying the project, a DMP can also form part of a funding application.

1.2 What information does a DMP contain?

- Information about the project and the individuals responsible for research data management
- Information on guidelines (e.g. institutional RDM policies, guidelines from funding bodies) and legal aspects (e.g. data protection, copyright, usage rights and related rights, contractual agreements)
- Information on collected and/or reused research data (data types, formats, volumes, methods, tools)
- Information on implementation and the infrastructures used for storage and data backup, versioning, the organization of data access and transfer, archiving, sharing and publication
- Description of the (discipline-specific) standards applied for the handling of research data, metadata and documentation guidelines
- Description of the ethical aspects of data collection and storage

¹ If you have any questions regarding the preparation of DMPs or advice on FDM applications, please contact [SaxFDM Advisory Services](#) or the FDM advisory offices at your institutions.

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SaxFDM-RDMO – STEP BY STEP

2.1 What is SaxFDM-RDMO²

The SaxFDM Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) helps you plan your data management. A structured questionnaire guides you through all aspects of data management, helping you maintain an overview and easily calculate the time and costs involved.

RDMO helps you:

- Create DMPs and FDM sections for your funding applications
- Plan data management in collaboration with project partners to meet your needs, and document responsibilities, tasks and agreements
- Use the snapshot function to create versioned DMPs, for example for funding bodies such as those under the EU Framework Program for Research and Innovation

2.2 Login

On the SaxFDM-RDMO website, log in using your institutional login details. You can log in via Shibboleth using your account at one of the SaxFDM member institutions. No separate login is required.

The image shows two screenshots. The top screenshot is the home page of dmp.saxfdm.de. It features the SaxFDM-RDMO logo and a 'Login' button highlighted with a green box. The bottom screenshot shows the NFDI login page, which includes a 'Welcome' message and a form for entering institutional login details, with a 'Proceed' button and options for other identity providers like Shibboleth and ORCID.

To log in to RDMO, click the 'Login' button on the right-hand side of the home page.

To log in, please select your home organization and, in the next step, enter your institution-specific login details.

² <https://dmp.saxfdm.de>

2.3 Homepage: My projects

Once you have successfully logged in, you will be taken to the RDMO homepage, where you can view an overview of all projects and functions created so far. If this is your first time logging in to RDMO and you have not yet created a DMP, you will not see any entries on this page.

2.4 Creating a new project (DMP)

Under 'My Projects', you will find all the DMPs that you have created yourself and/or to which you have been added as a member. You can also see when the plan was last edited. Using the icons to the right of the project details, you can continue editing a project or delete it.

In the right-hand column, by clicking on 'Create new project', you can create a new DMP, search for existing projects in the list, or import a DMP that has already been created using RDMO.

2.5 Your DMP: Options and settings

Once you have clicked on 'Create new project' on the homepage, you will be taken to a new page where you can fill in all the details describing your project.

The following information is required to create a new project:

Title

Give the DMP a meaningful name, ideally one that refers to the associated research project.

Description

Here you can describe your research project and the purpose of the associated DMP.

Questionnaire

Select a suitable questionnaire whose content your DMP is based on. Choose the questionnaire that best suits your project. The questions in a questionnaire cover all key aspects of the FDM that should be included in a DMP. You can change the questionnaire at any time later on.

Parent project

If you need to set up a DMP for your (sub)project or within complex project structures, you have the option of linking it to a parent project. This allows information to be automatically transferred.

Create new project

Title

The title for this project.

Description

A description for this project (optional).

Catalog

The catalog which will be used for this project.

SaxFDM Basic Checklist

This catalogue enables researchers to plan their data management across the whole data lifecycle according to the RDM basic requirements (e.g. FAIR principles). It covers the most important RDM activities and can be used as a basis for research projects or for further consulting regarding the handling of research data. The questions were created and provided by SaxFDM and are based on the DMP template developed by Science Europe (January, 2021). If you have any questions, please contact the [SaxFDM Competence Team](#) for further advice or the research data management team at your institution.

Horizon Europe

This catalog is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of answering the question on a dataset-specific basis. There is a suitable view for the output of the data management plan, which

- outputs the data management plan in the deliverable form desired by the EU;
- uses the original EU questions;
- automatically inserts references to questions that have already been asked in a similar form.

SaxFDM DFG Checklist

This catalog is based on the *RDM-checklist provided by the DFG*, supplemented by help texts, option sets with suggested texts and further information. The DFG checklist must be taken into account when submitting an application and when completing the project and is intended to help you to structure your data management. If you have any questions, please contact the [SaxFDM Competence Team](#) for further advice or the research data management team at your institution.

Software Management Plan for Researchers

This catalogue is for the management of scientific software projects. It supports scientists in the development and project organisation of software developments through fifty questions in different topic blocks. This is version 3.0 of the catalogue.

Parent project

The parent project of this project.

Create project

Cancel

The creation of a new project is complete once you confirm it by clicking on 'Create new project'. You have now created a new DMP. On the 'Project overview' page, you will find all the information you have entered so far, and in the right-hand panel you will see an overview of all the functions available to you for editing your project and/or viewing the questions and answers.

Test Project

Description	No description available.	
Catalog	<p>SaxFDM Basic Checklist</p> <p>This catalogues enables researchers to plan their data management across the whole data lifecycle according to the RDM basic requirements (e.g. FAIR principles). It covers the most important RDM activities and can be used as a basis for research projects or for further consulting regarding the handling of research data. The questions were created and provided by SaxFDM and are based on the DMP template developed by Science Europe (January, 2021). If you have any questions, please contact the <i>SaxFDM Competence Team</i> for further advice or the research data management team at your institution.</p>	

Options

Answer questions

View answers

- Update project information
- Update project catalog
- Update parent project
- Update project tasks
- Update project views
- Delete project

Add member

Create snapshot

[Back to projects overview](#)

Tasks

Tasks are generated automatically from the answers given in the project. On the page of each task you can see which of your answers lead to the activation of the task.

No active tasks found.

Views

Views are created using the answers given in the project and can then be exported in various formats. Initially, all views are empty. Please answer some questions by visiting **Answer Questions** (at the top of the sidebar).

View	Description	
SaxFDM Basic Checklist (English)		
DFG Checklist SaxFDM (English)		
Horizon Europe	View (export template) for the funding framework program "Horizon Europe" (2021-2027) of the European Commission (version 1.0, 5th May 2021)	
Testansicht		

Export

- RDMO XML
- CSV (comma separated)
- CSV (semicolon separated)
- JSON

Import values

Import from file

Members

Here you can see who can access the project and invite additional members. You can use the user roles to manage which rights the benefits have. Unless you are the last owner, you can leave the project with the button next to your name.

User	E-Mail	Role	

- RDMO XML
- CSV (comma separated)
- CSV (semicolon separated)
- JSON

Import values

Import from file

Snapshots

Snapshots allow you to save all responses at a given point in time and preserve a certain stage of the project. Later the snapshot can be used to create views, and the project can also be reset to a previous snapshot if needed.

No snapshots found.

The following features will help you create and edit your DMP:

Views

Views refer to templates that present the answers you and other project members have provided to the questionnaire in a continuous text format (in German and English). The displayed answers can be exported in various file formats. In addition, you can select specific questions and their answers, or customise the layout. The continuous text is suitable as a basis for the FDM chapter of a funding application, but should be adapted to your own writing style and revised.

Tasks

Tasks that arise in the FDM during the project period are automatically generated from the answers provided in the questionnaire – for example, contacting other relevant advisory bodies (such as the IT department, legal advice service or data protection officer) or creating project-specific standards – and can be assigned to individuals. Available tasks can be selected from a list.

Members

Memberships include all individuals who have access to a specific project or DMP. Each member can be assigned specific rights to edit a project or DMP via a role.

Snapshots

Snapshots allow you to save and view versions of your DMP at a specific point in time. This feature is useful if you wish to update DMPs regularly for project partners and/or funding bodies.

Please note: Deleting a project cannot be undone!

WHAT CATALOG SHOULD YOU USE?

SaxFDM DFG Checklist

(suitable for creating a text template for third-party funding applications)

This catalog is based on the RDM-checklist provided by the DFG, supplemented by help texts, option sets with suggested texts and further information. The DFG checklist must be taken into account when submitting an application and when completing the project and is intended to help you to structure your data management. If you have questions, contact the SaxFDM Team for further advice or the research data management team at your institution.

SaxFDM Basis Checklist

(A brief guide containing basic information on FDM, suitable as a basis for consultations and for your own project management)

This catalogue enables researchers to plan their data management across the whole data lifecycle according to the RDM basic requirements (e.g. FAIR principles). It covers the most important RDM activities and can be used as a basis for research projects or for further consulting regarding the handling of research data. The questions were created and provided by SaxFDM and are based on the DMP template developed by Science Europe (January, 2021). If you have any questions, please contact the SaxFDM Competence Team for further advice or the research data management team at your institution.

Horizon Europe

(suitable for creating a text template for third-party funding applications)

This catalog is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of answering the question on a dataset-specific basis. There is a suitable view for the output of the data management plan, which

- outputs the data management plan in the deliverable form desired by the EU;
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Software-Management-Plan for researchers

(for research software)

This catalogue is for the management of scientific software projects. It supports scientists in the development and project organisation of software developments through fifty questions in different topic blocks. This is version 3.0 of the catalogue.

2.6 Complete the questionnaire

When you click on 'Answer questions', you will be automatically redirected to the selected questionnaire. A questionnaire contains both open-ended questions and pre-defined answers from which you can choose. If you wish to enter a longer text, use the small icon at the bottom right of the text box to expand it..

You can see your progress in answering the questions in the right-hand sidebar.

The questionnaires are divided into thematic sections. You can find these here and under 'Navigation'.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a questionnaire. At the top, there is a breadcrumb trail: 'My Projects / Test Project / Institutional Affiliation'. The main heading is 'Institutional Affiliation'. Below it, there is a paragraph of instructions: 'Please choose the research institution where your project is based. To handle your project-specific research data, you should inform yourself about the (technical) infrastructures available at your institution. You will also need this information if you are applying for third-party funding. Therefore, please consult the relevant websites of your research institution or ask the responsible RDM team for advice on the available infrastructures. Please fill in the form for each tab. The same tabs may be used later on other pages. You can add a new tab using the green button. Once created, you can edit or delete tabs using the buttons in the top right corner.'

Below the instructions, there is a tabbed interface with two tabs: '#1' and '#2', and a '+ Set' button. The '#1' tab is active. The question is 'In which research institution is your project based?'. There are seven radio button options, each followed by a text input field:

- Following University: [input field]
- Following University of Applied Sciences: [input field]
- Following Helmholtz Institute: [input field]
- Following Leibniz Institute: [input field]
- Following Max-Planck Institute: [input field]
- University of Cooperative Education: [input field]
- Other research institution: [input field]

At the bottom right of the form, there are 'Back' and 'Proceed' buttons. To the right of the main form, there is a sidebar with three sections:

- Overview**: Project: Test Project, Catalog: SaxFDM Basic Checklist, Reload page, Back to my projects
- Progress**: 0 of 38, Back, Proceed
- Navigation**: Using the navigation will save your input. Grey entries will be conditionally skipped based on your input. Institutional Affiliation → Institutional Affiliation, Administrative Information, Data description, Storage and technical protection measu..., Data documentation, Legal aspects, Long-term data accessibility, Responsibilities and resources

Green callout boxes with lines pointing to the tabs and the sidebar are present. One callout points to the tabs with the text 'You can answer the questions in a catalogue for multiple datasets.' Another callout points to the sidebar with the text 'You can see your progress in answering the questions in the right-hand sidebar.' A third callout points to the navigation menu with the text 'The questionnaires are divided into thematic sections. You can find these here and under 'Navigation'.'

Your answers are saved automatically, and you can skip questions or return to them later at any time. Not all questions in a questionnaire are relevant to every project (e.g. questions on data protection). Whilst completing the questionnaire, you can navigate to previous or subsequent questions, as well as to other sections of the DMP. It is not always possible to complete all questions before or at the start of a project. You can therefore close RDMO at any time and continue answering the questions at a later date.

2.7 View and export responses

In the project overview, you can view your responses and check that they are complete. You can then export your responses, together with the questions, in various file formats, including PDF, RTF, MS Office or LaTeX. The project overview also allows you to export questions and responses as XML or CSV files. Please note that this function does not display the answers as continuous text. To do this, please use the 'View' function in the project overview.

Research Data Handling

Institutional Affiliation

For implementing an efficient research data management the infrastructures of the following research institution will be used in project area #1: Leipzig University; in project area #2: TU Dresden.

Project information

Data that is generated in the project receives funding by the following third party funding organisation in project area #1: DFG - German Research Foundation; in project area #2: DFG - German Research Foundation.

2.8. Additional features in SaxFDM-RDMO

Add members

If you wish to edit or share your DMP with other people, you can add members. To do this, use the 'Add members' option in the project overview. Enter the username and email address of the person you wish to add to your DMP project. You must then specify the role the member should have. The following options are available:

Owner: Usually creates the project and has full rights; this role can also be assigned to new members

Manager: Can answer questions and create snapshots, export the project, import values and update project settings, but cannot delete projects.

Author: Can answer questions.

Guest: Has read-only access.

You can view an overview of all members in the project overview, where project owners can also remove members.

Creating Snapshots

A snapshot is a record that saves the current status of your DMP project at a specific point in time. Once you have saved all the answers to a questionnaire, you can no longer revert to an earlier

version of the DMP. Snapshots allow you to track and save all versions of your DMP. To create a snapshot, please click on 'Create snapshot' in the right-hand menu bar in the project overview. Give the snapshot a title and describe it if necessary. You will find all created snapshots in your project overview.

CONTACT AND FURTHER INFORMATION

If you have any questions or suggestions regarding the SaxFDM-RDMO, please contact:
kontakt@saxfdm.de

For any other questions regarding research data management, please contact the SaxFDM team or your local FDM advisory service.

Comprehensive further information on the creation of DMPs can be found, amongst other places, on the forschungsdaten.info portal. Training materials for SaxFDM-RDMO can be found in the [SaxFDM community](#) on Zenodo.